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A Decade in the Classroom

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Ten years I've stood before eager eyes,
In a public school where dreams arise.
Each lesson shaped by hands that care,
In crowded rooms, the burdens we bear.

The weight of the world in chalk and dust,
With every student, I build their trust.
Late nights, papers spread like stars,
Grading dreams, erasing scars.

At home, a different battle waits,
Two sons, a daughter, and life's weights.
My partner, brave in uniform blue,
Fights his battles, while I fight through.

Balancing worlds, I strive to be,
The teacher they need, the mother they see.
Through sleepless nights and quiet fears,
Fulfillment rises, with love and tears.

For in the struggle, joy is found,
In every "thank you," so profound.
Ten years, and still I stand tall,
For the hearts I've touched, that's worth it all.

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